

The Role of Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme in Tribal Development – A Study With Reference to Siddeshwara Hills, Erode District

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Abstract – The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS) is a key rural development initiative aimed at providing wage employment and improving livelihoods. This study explores its role in the socio-economic development of tribal communities Siddeshwara Hills, Erode District, focusing on employment generation, income enhancement, and rural asset creation. Tribal populations often face challenges like poverty, lack of resources, and seasonal migration. MGNREGS helps address these issues by ensuring job security and infrastructure development. Through an analysis of implementation and impact, this research highlights the scheme's benefits and challenges while suggesting policy improvements to enhance its effectiveness in tribal regions for sustainable development.

Keywords - MGNREGS, Tribal development, Rural employment, Livelihood security, Asset creation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tribal communities in India generally live in remote and economically backward regions with limited employment opportunities. Seasonal unemployment, poverty, and migration are common concerns. MGNREGS was introduced to address these issues by providing wage employment and building rural assets.

Siddeshwara Hills in Erode District is largely inhabited by tribal families whose primary livelihood sources are agriculture, daily labour, and forestry. This study attempts to evaluate how far MGNREGS has helped these communities in improving their standard of living and securing sustainable livelihoods.

Significance of The Study

Mgnregs is a major social security initiative of the Government of India. It provides regular income, reduces poverty, prevents migration, and supports women's empowerment. For tribal communities, this scheme is especially important because:

- It ensures employment opportunities
- It supports basic income security
- It helps in asset creation like roads, water facilities, and land development
- It improves living standards and social inclusion

Hence, this study is relevant to understand its real impact in Siddeshwara Hills.

Statement of The Problem

Even after many years of implementation, many tribal families still struggle for stable income and livelihood opportunities. Industrial and business activities are limited in hilly regions. Therefore, tribals depend largely on MGNREGS for their livelihood. However, issues such as wage delay, lack of awareness, limited facilities at worksite, and irregular employment still exist. This study analyses the actual benefits and existing problems faced by tribal beneficiaries.

Objectives of The Study

- To study the socio-economic profile of tribal respondents.
- To analyse the awareness of MGNREGS among tribal communities.
- To assess the role of MGNREGS in improving their living standards.
- To measure the level of satisfaction of the respondents.
- To provide suggestions for better implementation of the scheme.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is descriptive in nature.

Area of Study: Siddeshwara Hills, Erode District

Respondents: Tribal beneficiaries of MGNREGS

Sample Size: 150 beneficiaries of MGNREGS

Sampling technique: Non-probability convenience sampling method.

• Secondary Data: Government reports, journals, articles, records.

Simple percentage analysis and tables were used to interpret the results.

Data Source:

• Primary Data: Collected through structured questionnaire.

Data Analysis & Interpretation

S.No	Factor	Categories	No.of Respondents	Percentage	Interpretation
1	Gender	Male	68	45%	Majority are Females
		Female	82	55%	
2	Age	18–20	33	22%	Majority are 51+
		21–30	17	11%	
		31–40	7	5%	
		41–50	31	20%	
		51 & Above	63	42%	
3	Marital Status	Married	96	64%	Majority Married
		Unmarried	43	28%	
		Divorced	2	1%	
		Widow/Widower	9	6%	
4	Education	No Formal Education	51	34%	Majority Uneducated
		Primary School	29	19%	
		Secondary	31	21%	
		High School	39	26%	
5	Tribe	Gond	44	29%	Gond Highest
		Kolam	36	24%	
		Andha	37	25%	
		Paradhan	34	22%	
6	Occupation	Farmer	66	44%	Majority Farmers
		Agricultural Labour	47	31%	
		Private Worker	37	25%	
7	Family Type	Nuclear	82	55%	Nuclear Dominates
		Joint	68	45%	
8	Annual Income	₹20,001–₹39,000	59	39%	Majority Low Income
		₹39,001–₹40,000	27	18%	
		₹40,001–₹50,000	22	14%	
		₹50,001 & Above	43	29%	
9	Family Size	1	6	4%	Majority 5 Members
		2	21	14%	
		3	26	17%	
		4	35	23%	
		5	63	42%	
10	Awareness	Yes	130	86%	Awareness High
		No	20	14%	
11	Source of Information	TV	36	24%	Neighbours Major Source
		Newspaper	30	20%	
		Neighbours	37	25%	
		Friends	35	24%	
		Others	10	7%	
12	Members Working	1–2	75	50%	Majority 1–2
		3–4	65	43%	

S.No	Factor	Categories	No.of Respondents	Percentage	Interpretation
					Members
		5+	10	7%	
13	Job Card	Yes	92	61%	Majority Have Card
		No	58	39%	
14	Charges Paid	Yes	90	60%	Indicates Corruption
		No	60	40%	
15	Time Taken	15 Days	50	33%	Max Within 15 Days
		30 Days	42	28%	
		40 Days	36	24%	
		60 Days	22	15%	
16	Faced Problem	Yes	52	35%	Majority No Issues
		No	98	65%	
17	Daily Wages	50–100	27	18%	Majority ₹201+
		101–150	34	23%	
		151–200	39	26%	
		201 & Above	50	33%	
18	Wages On Time	Yes	103	68%	Mostly On-time
		No	47	32%	
19	Tribal Development	Yes	88	59%	Positive Effect
		No	62	41%	
20	Primary Income	MGNREGS	63	42%	MGNREGS Major
		Agriculture	43	29%	
		Labour	20	13%	
		Govt Job	6	4%	
		Private Job	9	6%	
		Self Employment	9	6%	
21	Livestock	Cow	66	44%	Cows Highest
		Buffalo	39	26%	
		Bull Pair	31	21%	
		None	14	9%	
22	Animal Husbandry	Yes	98	65%	Majority Have
		No	52	35%	
23	Worksite Facilities	First Aid	46	31%	Shed Highest
		Shed	49	33%	
		Water	40	26%	
		Creche	15	10%	
24	Type of Work	Water Conservation	44	30%	Water Conservation Highest
		Rural Connectivity	31	21%	
		Forest Work	27	18%	
		Tank Work	23	15%	
		Plantation	16	10%	
		Land Development	9	6%	
25	Regular Work	Yes	99	66%	Majority Receive Work
		No	51	34%	
26	Satisfaction	Yes	89	59%	Majority Satisfied
		No	61	41%	
27	Impact	Employment	53	35%	

S.No	Factor	Categories	No.of Respondents	Percentage	Interpretation
		Reduced Migration	53	35%	
		Domestic Economy Help	31	21%	
		Increase Income	13	9%	Employment & Migration Benefit
28	Challenges	Delayed Wages	51	34%	
		Lack Jobs	44	29%	
		Poor Conditions	36	24%	
		Corruption	19	13%	Delay Major Issue
29	Scheme Improvement Rank	Transparency & Accountability	75	50%	Rank 1
		Working Conditions	30	20%	Rank 2
		More Workdays	25	17%	Rank 3
		Higher Wages	20	13%	Rank 4
30	Chi-Square Result	Calculated Value = 6.17	–	–	No Significant Relationship
		Table Value = 16.91	–	–	Marital Status Not Related

Findings

- MGNREGS provides regular employment and income support.
- It plays a major role in livelihood security of tribal families.
- Women actively participate and benefit equally.
- Infrastructure and community assets have improved.
- Awareness levels have improved but still need strengthening.
- Major challenges include delayed wages, limited working days, and lack of proper facilities.

Suggestions

- Wages should be paid on time without delay.
- Awareness camps should be conducted regularly.
- Work opportunities should be provided continuously.
- Proper facilities like drinking water, shade, and first aid should be ensured.
- Monitoring and supervision must be strengthened.
- More skill-based activities can be included to improve productivity.

III. CONCLUSION

MGNREGS has emerged as a strong livelihood support system for tribal communities in Siddeshwara Hills. It has improved income levels, reduced unemployment, empowered women, and contributed to social and economic development. Although certain administrative and implementation challenges exist, strengthening the scheme will further enhance tribal welfare and sustainable development.

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